

**Toxic and Ecological Risks of Bisphenol A and Its Analogs in Marine Environments:
Evidence from the Sea Urchin *Arbacia lixula***

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**Toxic and Ecological Risks of Bisphenol A and Its Analogs in Marine Environments:
Evidence from the Sea Urchin *Arbacia lixula***

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Abstract

In this study, the embryotoxic, spermyotoxic and genotoxic effects of BPA and its three analogs [(Bisphenol B (BPB), Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE) and Bisphenol F diglycidyl ether (BFDGE)] were comparatively evaluated at environmentally relevant concentrations (0,1-2 µg /L) using the sea urchin *Arbacia lixula*. The findings suggest that BPA, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE (EC₅₀ embryo: 1,396 µg- BPA/L, 0.205 µg- BPB/L, 0.474 µg- BADGE/L and 0.944 µg- BFDGE/L 33.32-43.32 mg L⁻¹ and EC₅₀ for sperms were determined as, 0.169 µg BPB/L, 0.68 µg BADGE/L and 14,202 µg BFDGE/L) show strong toxic effects towards *A. lixula*. Cytological analyses revealed statistically significant alterations in both cytotoxicity and genotoxicity related parameters in embryos exposed to all tested compounds compared to the control group. The calculated RQ values indicating a high ecological risk for BPA and its analogs BPB, BADGE and BFDGE in the marine environment. These findings demonstrate that BPA alternatives are not necessarily safer than BPA and may pose substantial risks to marine invertebrates even at low concentrations. the significance of bisphenols-induced toxicity extends beyond marine ecosystems to human health.

Key Words: *Arbacia lixula*, Bisphenol B, Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether , Bisphenol F diglycidyl ether, Toxicity

1. Introduction

Marine invertebrates, particularly in the early stages of life, are highly sensitive to chemical stressors and are therefore widely used as indicator organisms for ecological risk assessment. For the survival of species and, consequently, the functionality of ecosystems, the successful occurrence of gametogenesis, fertilization, and the development of larvae into healthy young and adult individuals is crucial (Bögner 2016). Sea urchins are one of the preferred model organisms for developmental biology studies. Fertilization and larval development of sea urchins have, therefore, been extensively studied (Pagano et al., 1986; Matranga et al., 2011). Disruptions observed at these endpoints are considered reliable indicators of population-level impacts and degradation of ecosystem health.

Bisphenol A (BPA) is an emerging organic compound used in the production of epoxy resin, polycarbonate plastics and thermal paper. BPA is generally used to provide hardness, strength, and resistance to materials used in the production of many consumer products, including food containers, baby feeding bottles, medical devices, electronics, dental fillings, toys, water pipes, and paints (Xing et al. 2022). Many studies have reported that BPA is a xenoestrogen that mimics the effects of natural estrogen (17- β estradiol) and negatively impacts the endocrine, reproductive, metabolic, and nervous systems (Abraham and Chakraborty 2020; Mukhopadhyat et al. 2021; Hamed and Li 2022). In addition to its endocrine-disrupting effects, it has also been shown by Czarny-Krzyminska et al. (2023) to cause genotoxicity and oxidative stress in aquatic organisms. The significance of bisphenols-induced toxicity extends beyond marine ecosystems to human health. The molecular and cellular pathways affected by bisphenols in sea urchin embryos such as DNA damage, chromosomal alterations, and impaired cell division are evolutionarily conserved and closely resemble mechanisms involved in human reproductive disorders, developmental abnormalities, and carcinogenesis (Diamanti-Kandarakis et al., 2009; Gore et al., 2015). Studies have linked bisphenol exposure in humans to decreased fertility, altered embryonic development, and increased genotoxic risk, reinforcing the value of marine biological testing as an early warning system for human health hazards (Peretz et al., 2014; Wassenaar & Legler, 2017). Furthermore, the presence of bisphenols in seafood and marine-derived products highlights a direct exposure pathway for humans, revealing a link between ecological pollution and public health risk (Toptanci et al., 2022, Santonicola et al., 2021). The presence of BPA and its analogs in aquatic ecosystems indicates that they can migrate from BPs based materials (polycarbonates and epoxy resins) during diffusion and hydrolysis in high temperatures and acidic/alkaline environments after human activities (Huang et al., 2012), the production, use, and disposal of products based on them (Liu et al., 2021), and their discharge into the aquatic environment. BPA concentrations in sea water range from 0,0027 to 100 μ g/L (Czarny-Krzyminska et al., 2023). BPA concentrations in Turkey's freshwater reported as 29,920- 7480 ng/L and a wide range of BPA levels have been observed in surface and deep seawater around Turkey 16,920 ng/L (Ozhan & Kocaman 2019). BADGE, BFDGE and BPB were used as alternative materials in "BPA-free" products. The increasing annual total production of BADGE, BFDGE and BPB used especially in food packaging, storage, and transport products, poses a risk of toxicity due to food contamination and is a concern for public health (Hutler Wolkowicz et al., 2016; Teresaki et al., 2006). BPB had the most similar structure to BPA and it is used in Europe for coating food and beverage cans (Pelch et al. 2019, Grumetto et al., 2008). Danzl et al. (2009) reported that the persistence of BPB in aquatic environments is higher than that of BPA. Zhou et al. (2020) reported that BPB has lower biodegradation than BPA in surface water and river sediments. BPB was found in 0.0180–0.0460 μ g/L surface water in China and wastewater between 0 to 0.0055 μ g/L in India (Karthikraj & Kannan 2017). BADGE is mainly used in storage vessels, as the lacquer coatings on food cans (Ballesteros-

Gómez et al., 2007) and used in cosmetics, cleaners and plastic bowls (Park & Yeo 2012). Several studies have been carried out concerning BADGE and BFDGE in canned food, mainly seafood products in Turkey (Toptancı et al. 2022). Levels of BADGE and BFDGE were reported in wastewater influents at concentrations from 0.00096 mg/L-0.0016 mg/L (Ballesteros-Gómez et al. 2007). Because of BADGE and BFDGE's different uses and its high production worldwide, it is relevant to know the risk to wildlife after epoxy resins reach the environment (Abessa et al. 2025). There is no study to determine its effect on the aquatic environment and especially sea urchin *A. lixula*. Marine ecosystems are especially vulnerable to bisphenol contamination due to continuous inputs from industrial effluents, urban runoff, and plastic debris degradation. Sea urchins are well-established marine model organisms in ecotoxicology due to their external fertilization and rapid development, to environmental contaminants. Therefore, the present study aims to assess and compare the toxic and genotoxic effects of BPA and selected BPA analogues using both sperm bioassay, embryotoxic and cytogenetic/genotoxic endpoints in the sea urchin *Arbacia lixula*.

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, BPA and its alternatives, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE were investigated. Assays conducted to determine the embryotoxic, spermyotoxic and cytotoxic/genotoxic effects of the selected chemicals on sea urchins.

Chemicals

Bisphenol A (BPA; 4,4'-Isopropylidenediphenol; 80-05-7), Bisphenol B (BPB; 77-40-7, Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE; 1675-54-3 and Bisphenol F diglycidyl ether (BFDGE; 2095-03-6) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Co. Test chemicals were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (Sigma, Cat. No: 67-68-5).

Test concentrations were prepared by adding the chemicals from stock solution directly to the test medium. Test concentrations of the chemicals were selected based on insights from Czarny-Krzywińska et al., (2023) and Szczepańska et al., (2018). Assessing ecotoxicity and the endocrine potential of selected phthalates, BADGE and BFDGE derivatives in relation to environmentally detectable levels. *Science of the Total Environment*, 610, 854-866. as; 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1, 1.5 and 2 µg/L of BPA, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE according to environmentally relevant concentrations

Sea Urchins

Specimens of *A. lixula* were collected manually from the coastal zone of Seferihisar, İzmir, Turkey. Seawater from their natural habitat were also collected to maintain the organisms in a familiar environment during laboratory examinations. Before the biotests water samples were subjected to filtration using a 0.45 µm filter to eliminate particulate matter. Following methodologies established by Arslan and Parlak (2007), spermyotoxicity, genotoxicity/cytotoxicity and embryotoxicity assays were conducted in controlled settings.

Spermyotoxicity Assay

Fertilization Success and Offspring Quality

A 50 µl sample was taken from a concentrated sperm mass filtered through a 30 µm mesh and placed in FSW containing toxicants at increasing concentrations, as well as a toxicant-free

(negative control) and CdCl₂ (positive control) solution prepared approximately one hour earlier. The sperm were incubated in these environments for 30 minutes, and 100 µl was taken from these sperm solutions and added to 20 ml of FSW containing eggs that had not been exposed to the toxicant (approximately 50 eggs/ml). In the spermyotoxicity assay, polystyrene cups with a volume of 50 ml were used, and this material was not reused to prevent contamination. The results were evaluated based on sperm fertilization success and offspring quality. Changes in the fertilization success of exposed sperm were determined by scoring the percentage of fertilized eggs. When determining fertilization success, the Fertilization Rate (FR = % fertilized eggs) has been taken for account. Offspring qualities were observed on living plutei, which were immobilized in 10⁻⁴ M chromium sulphate as classified in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Related *A. lixula*: A) Fertilized egg; B) Unfertilized egg (Arslan 2005).

Embryotoxicity Assay

Controls accompanying the experiments were untreated negative controls (filtered natural seawater collected from the same area as the echinoids: FSW) and 3x10⁻⁴M CdCl₂ as a positive control. Embryos were also exposed to DMSO as a solvent control, being added to the medium in the same volume as the highest test concentration of BPs, and no effect was detected on the development of sea urchin embryos. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was employed as a solvent for the test chemicals, introducing an additional control within the experimental framework to account for any potential confounding effects of the solvent at a concentration of 0.1 % (v: v). All treatments were tested as six replicates in six well-plates. For embryotoxicity tests, chemicals and suspended in 9 ml FSW were added each culture plate well and then 1 ml of zygotes (Figure 1) was added to medium and incubated at 19 ± 2 °C in the dark for 72 h. After a 72h incubation, 10⁻⁴ M chromium sulphate was added to the culture wells and the larvae were scored on an Bx51 Olympus microscope (1000×).

Figure 2. Developmental abnormalities observed in *A. lixula* during embryogenesis (N: Normal individual, P2: Abnormal blastula or gastrula; P1: Skeletal system abnormalities, R: Retarded).

Embryonic/larval developmental defects were scored in 100 random embryos of each test group was observed under a light microscope to determine the embryotoxic effects of the test chemicals, as classified in Figure 2. Embryotoxicity was assessed on 72-hour old pluteus larvae according to morphological criteria defined by Pagano et al. (1993). Developmental defects were observed on living plutei, which were immobilized in 10^{-4} M chromium sulphate.

Cytogenetic Assay

In the genotoxicity tests conducted with *A. lixula*, the stages of culture were carried out as specified in the embryotoxicity testing section. However, the embryos were fixed with "Carnoy's solution (Absolute ethanol: Chloroform: Acetic Acid = 6:3:1)" approximately 5-6 hours after fertilization. About half an hour after fixation, the Carnoy's solution was removed and replaced with absolute ethanol. After 24 hours, the ethanol was renewed, and the embryos were stored in this manner until microscopic observations. Cytogenetic analyses were performed by randomly selecting 30 embryos from each culture medium. For this purpose, the embryos were stained with acetocarmine and then examined under a light microscope (x1000) with the aid of immersion oil immediately after staining.

Table I. Cytological and Morphological Evaluation Criteria Used for Embryotoxicity and Genotoxicity Assessment (Arslan and Parlak 2008).

Quantitative Criteria	Morphological Criteria
a) Average number of mitoses per embryo EDM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total mitotic abnormalities per embryo TMB • Anaphase bridge • Lagging chromosome • Free chromosome • Chromosome breakage/fragmentation • Multipolar spindle <p>Acentric fragment</p>
b) Percentage of interphase embryos %IE	
c) Metaphase/Anaphase ratio M/A	
	b) Percentage of embryos with >1 mitotic abnormality %E(+mb)

Mitotic activity (numbers of metaphase and anaphase) and chromosome aberrations (chromosome bridges, lagging chromosomes, multipolar spindles, free chromosome sets, fragmented chromosomes) were scored in each embryo, thus allowing to assess both quantitative endpoints and mitotic anomalies (Table I).

Risk Factor Calculation

The risk quotient (RQ) method, proposed by the European technical guidance document, was used to assess the impact of Bisphenols on the aquatic environment. The RQ was calculated as follow (Wang et al. 2024): a) $PNEC = NOEC / AF$ b) $RQ = MEC / PNEC$

MEC: the measured environmental concentration

PNEC: the predicted no-effect concentration

NOEC: the no-observed effect concentration in chronic toxicity.

AF: the assessment factor, in this study based on the standard protocols (European Commission 2003).

In this study, to assess the potential hazard of BPB more strictly, the risk was divided into three grades: $RQ > 1$ = high risk, $0.1 < RQ < 1$ = moderate risk, and $RQ < 0.1$ = low risk (Zhao et al. 2019). (Zhao et al. 2019).

Statistical Analysis

EPA Probit Analysis Program used for calculating LC/EC Values Version 1.5. Dunnett's tests were used to compare the differences in the frequency distribution of the evaluated parameters (N: normal plutei, R: retarded plutei, P1: skeletal malformations, P2: blocked gastrula or blastula and D: dead) between the negative control (FSW) and the treatment groups by applying the logarithmic transformation to normalize distributions.

3. Results

3.1 Embryotoxicity

Microscopic observation of embryos exposed to BPA during embryogenesis revealed significant abnormalities and toxic effects at concentrations ranging from 0,1-2 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Embryotoxicity tests showed that increasing concentrations of BPA reduced the normal development of sea urchins (*A. lixula*), as demonstrated by the dose-response curve (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Embryotoxic effects of BPs on *A. lixula* normal plutei frequencies

In the first two BPA concentrations, the low frequencies increase observed in skeletal system disorders showed a rapid increase at 0,8 µg/L. Embryos that were blocked at the blastula and gastrula stages observed at 1,5 and 2,0 µg/L ($p < 0.005$). Compared to the control group, concentrations of 0,4 and 0,8 µg/L BPA generally caused skeletal malformations ($p < 0.001$). While larval malformations (P1) were not observed at BPA concentrations of 2 µg/L, the blocked at the gastrula stage (P2) reached 100 %. (Figure). After logarithmic transformation of the obtained data, the effective concentration (EC50), Low effective concentration (LOEC) and no observed effect concentrations (NOEC) of BPA were calculated as: 1,396 µg-BPA/L, 0,26 µg-BPA/L and 0,071 µg-BPA/L.

Figure 4. Developmental arrest exposed to BPs on *A. lixula* embryo development.

Microscopic observation of embryos exposed to BPB during embryogenesis revealed significant abnormalities and toxic effects. Embryotoxicity tests showed that increasing concentrations of BPB slowly reduced the normal development of *A. lixula* by approximately 20 %, as demonstrated by the dose-response curve (Figure 3). Compared to the control group, lower concentrations generally caused skeletal malformations 0,2 µg-BPB/L ($p < 0.001$). At the highest concentrations, the percentage of blocked embryo at blastula stage reached the 100 % (2 µg- BPB/L) (Figure 4). The effective concentration (EC50), Low effective concentration (LOEC) and no observed effect concentrations (NOEC) of BPB was calculated as: 0,205 µg-BPA/L, 0,081 µg-BPA/L and 0,038 µg/L.

As a result of the biotests conducted, a decrease in normal pluteus frequencies was observed in proportion to the increasing amount of BADGE. The dose-response relationship is quite good depending on the chemical amount (Figures 3). With the beginning of the increase in BADGE concentration, skeletal system disorders (P1) started to be observed. In embryos exposed to 0,1 µg-BADGE/L, the frequency of normal pluteus was found to be approximately 78 %. When the frequency of normal pluteus at this concentration was compared with the negative control group, a statistically significant toxic effect was detected ($p < 0.05$). In sea urchin embryos exposed to the highest concentration of 2 µg/L BADGE, normal pluteus was not observed at a frequency of 0 % ($p < 0.0001$), while 100 % were typically arrested in development at the gastrula and blastula stages (Figure 4). After the obtained data were transformed into a logarithmic transformation, the EC 50 concentration of BADGE was calculated as 0,474 µg-BADGE/L.

In embryos exposed to BFDGE, the frequency of normal pluteus was found to be approximately 73 ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 3). Additionally, individuals with skeletal system deformities were observed at a frequency of 26% (0,1 µg/L) and individuals whose development had stopped at the gastrula stage were observed at a frequency of 0.5%. At 0,4 µg- BFDGE/L, the frequency of normal pluteus decreased by about 15%, dropping to 59% . Corresponding to this decrease, the frequency of individuals with skeletal system deformities increased by 15%, reaching 41% ($p < 0.005$). In embryos exposed to 0,8 µg/L BFDGE, skeletal system abnormalities were observed at a high rate. In sea urchin embryos exposed to the highest concentration of BFDGE, no normal pluteus was detected (0% frequency, $p < 0.001$), and 100% of pluteus observed were arrested in the gastrula and blastula stages (Figure 4). the EC/LC50 concentration of BFDGE was calculated as 0,944 µg-BFDGE/L

When comparing the effective concentrations of all chemicals that completed embryotoxicity tests among themselves and with BPA, it was determined that BPA derivatives are more toxic than BPA itself and cause skeletal system abnormalities and developmental arrests in sea urchin larvae . When comparing the all-bisphenol analogs according to EC50 values, as $BPB > BADGE > BFDGE > BPA$

Spermyotoxicity

As a result of the fertilization success evaluates, the dose-response curve (Figure 5) showed a decreased percentage of fertilized eggs at BPs concentrations when compared with the control group. Significant changes were observed in the fertilization rates compared with control group ($p < 0,005$). Embryos in the DMSO group exhibited high fertilization rates (95–100%), indicating that the solvent did not interfere with the fertilization process. BPA exposure resulted concentration-dependent decrease in fertilization success, with a sharp reduction observed from 1 µg/L onwards and fertilization rates declining to 30–40% at higher concentrations. In contrast,

BPB induced a moderate but progressive decrease in fertilization rate across increasing concentrations, although fertilization remained above 70% even at the highest exposure levels. BADGE and BFDGE showed only slight reductions in fertilization success, with high fertilization rates maintained throughout most of the tested concentration range and modest declines observed only at the highest concentrations (1-2 µg/L). Overall, the inhibitory effect on fertilization followed the order BPA > BPB > BADGE ≥ BFDGE, demonstrating marked differences in spermyotoxic potential among the tested bisphenol compounds.

In this study, sperm exposure was evaluated for the effects of BPs on offspring quality. As a result of the spermyotoxicity tests, the dose-response curve (Figure 10) showed a decreased percentage of normal pluteus. The scores of developmental defects of larvae generated by BPA exposed sperm showed that offspring quality was significantly decreased at all concentrations assessed ($p < 0.005$).

Figure 5. Effects of Bisphenols on fertilization success of sea urchin *A. lixula*

Offspring quality, expressed as the percentage of normal larvae, was significantly affected by exposure to BPA in *A. lixula* (Figure 6). Control embryos exhibited high proportions of normal larvae (95–100%), indicating normal embryonic and larval development, whereas cadmium chloride (CdCl_2) caused a pronounced reduction, confirming its strong toxic effect. All bisphenol compounds induced a concentration-dependent decrease in the percentage of normal larvae. BPs produced the most pronounced effect, with a marked reduction observed from 0.2 µg/L onwards and an almost complete inhibition of normal larval development at concentrations ≥ 1 µg/L. BPB also significantly impaired larval quality, although normal larvae were still detected at intermediate concentrations (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Effects of BPA on offspring of *A. lixula* (exposed sperms)

Figure 7. Effects of BPB on offspring of *A. lixula* (exposed sperms)

Figure 8. Effects of BADGE on offspring of *A. lixula* (exposed sperms)

Figure 9. Effects of BFDGE on offspring of *A. lixula* (exposed sperms)

Figure 10. Spermytotoxic effects of BPs on normal plutei frequencies

BADGE exposure resulted in a moderate but progressive decline in normal larval percentages with increasing concentration. In contrast, BFDGE exhibited the weakest effect, with high proportions of normal larvae maintained at low and intermediate concentrations and a noticeable decrease occurring only at higher exposure levels (Figure 8,9).

Table II. Effective Concentrations of BPA and its analogues on Sea urchin *A. lixula*

Chemicals	Embryotoxicity (µg/L)			Spermytoxicity		
	NOEC	LOEC	EC/LC50	NOEC	LOEC	EC/LC50
BPA	0,071	0,26	1,396	0,010	0,031	0,201
BPB	0,038	0,081	0,205	0,005	0,023	0,169
BADGE	0,09	0,19	0,474	0,017	0,089	0,68
BFDGE	0,466	0,64	0,944	0,039	0,10	14,20

Overall, the severity of developmental toxicity followed the order $BPB \geq BPA > BADGE > BFDGE$, indicating compound-specific differences in spermytotoxic potential among the tested bisphenol analogs (Figure 10, Table II). EC50 value of BPs shown in Table II, Results bring us a conclusion that the Bisphenols has less effects on fertilization success of sperm, but extremely decreased offspring quality of exposed sperms became more important from the ecotoxicological point of view.

Cytogenetic toxicity

The cytological analysis revealed significant alterations in both cytotoxicity-related parameters (EDM, %IE, and M/A) and genotoxicity-related parameters (%E(+mb)) in embryos exposed to the tested compounds compared with the control group. A concentration-dependent decrease in EDM values was observed, indicating a marked suppression of mitotic activity. Concurrently, %IE values significantly increased, reflecting cell cycle arrest and inhibition of cell proliferation. Furthermore, notable changes in the M/A ratio were detected, suggesting disturbances in mitotic spindle formation and progression through metaphase and anaphase stages. Mitotic activity, expressed as mitosis per embryo (%MPE), was significantly affected

by exposure to bisphenol compounds in *Arbacia lixula* embryos (Figure 11). Control embryos exhibited high mitotic rates (19–20% MPE), indicating normal embryonic cell division, whereas cadmium (Cd), used as a positive control, caused a pronounced and statistically significant reduction in mitotic activity (~3% MPE; $p < 0.05$), confirming its strong cytotoxic and antimitotic properties. Embryos exposed to DMSO showed mitotic values comparable to the control group, with no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$), demonstrating that the solvent did not interfere with embryonic mitosis. All tested bisphenol compounds (BPA, BADGE, BFDGE and BPB) induced a concentration-dependent decrease in %MPE, with statistically significant reductions observed from the lowest tested concentration (0.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$) onwards ($p < 0.05$). BPA caused a moderate but progressive inhibition of mitotic activity across increasing concentrations, whereas BADGE and BFDGE resulted in a more pronounced suppression of mitosis, particularly at medium and high exposure levels. Among the tested compounds, BPB exhibited the strongest antimitotic effect, leading to the lowest %MPE values at higher concentrations (4–8 $\mu\text{g/L}$), which were significantly different from both the control and BPA-treated groups ($p < 0.05$). Overall, the magnitude of mitotic inhibition followed the order $\text{BPB} \geq \text{BFDGE} \geq \text{BADGE} > \text{BPA}$, highlighting distinct toxic potencies among bisphenol analogs.

Figure 11. Mitotic division per embryo in *P. lividus* embryos exposed to increasing concentrations of Bisphenols (during embryogenesis).

Figure 12. % Interphase embryos in *P. lividus* embryos exposed to increasing concentrations of Bisphenols during embryogenesis.

The percentage of embryos remaining in interphase (%IE) was significantly affected by exposure to bisphenol compounds in *A. lixula* embryos (Figure 12). Control embryos exhibited an extremely low proportion of interphase cells (approximately 1%), reflecting normal and continuous cell cycle progression. All tested bisphenol compounds (BPA, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE) caused a concentration-dependent increase in %IE, with statistically significant differences observed from 0.2 µg/L onwards ($p < 0.05$). BPA induced a moderate elevation in interphase frequency, even at the highest tested concentration. In contrast, BPB produced the strongest effect, resulting in the highest %IE values across all concentrations, particularly at medium and high doses (0,5–2 µg/L). BADGE and BFDGE also significantly increased the proportion of embryos arrested in interphase, although to a lesser extent than BPB. Overall, the magnitude of interphase accumulation followed the order BPB > BADGE > BFDGE > BPA.

Figure 13. Effects of bisphenol compounds on the metaphase/anaphase (M/A) ratio in *A. lixula* embryos.

The metaphase/anaphase (M/A) ratio was significantly altered in *Arbacia lixula* embryos following exposure to bisphenol compounds (Figure 13). Control embryos exhibited a stable M/A ratio of approximately 2.5, indicating balanced progression between metaphase and anaphase. In contrast, cadmium (Cd), used as a positive control, induced a marked increase in the M/A ratio (≈ 4.7), demonstrating a strong metaphase arrest. Embryos treated with DMSO showed M/A values comparable to the control group, confirming that the solvent did not affect mitotic phase distribution. Exposure to bisphenol compounds resulted in concentration-dependent changes in the M/A ratio. BPA caused a slight reduction in the M/A ratio at low and intermediate concentrations, followed by an increase at the highest concentration assessed (8 $\mu\text{g/L}$). In contrast, BPB produced a pronounced and dose-dependent elevation of the M/A ratio, with significantly higher values observed at concentrations $\geq 1 \mu\text{g/L}$ compared to the control ($p < 0.05$). BADGE exposure led to a moderate but consistent increase in the M/A ratio with increasing concentration, whereas BFDGE induced a biphasic response, characterized by elevated M/A values at intermediate concentrations and a reduction at the highest doses. Overall, the magnitude of metaphase accumulation followed the order $\text{BPB} > \text{BADGE} > \text{BFDGE} \approx \text{BPA}$.

Figure 14. The number of embryos with multiple mitotic disorders in *P. lividus* embryos exposed to increasing concentrations of BADGE during embryogenesis.

The percentage of embryos exhibiting one or more mitotic disorders [%E(+mb) ≥ 1] increased significantly in *Arbacia lixula* embryos following exposure to bisphenol compounds (Figure 14). Control and DMSO-treated embryos showed negligible %E(+mb) ≥ 1 values, indicating genetic stability and the absence of solvent-induced genotoxicity. All bisphenol compounds induced a concentration-dependent increase in %E(+mb) ≥ 1 starting from the lowest tested concentration (0.2 µg/L). BADGE and BFDGE elicited the strongest genotoxic responses, with a steep increase observed at low concentrations and high %E(+mb) ≥ 1 values recorded at medium and high exposure levels. BPB also produced a marked genotoxic effect, although to a lesser extent than BADGE and BFDGE. In contrast, BPA induced only a weak response, with minimal increases observed at low and intermediate concentrations and a moderate elevation detected only at the highest concentration evaluated (8 µg/L). Overall, the genotoxic potency of the tested compounds followed the order BADGE ≥ BFDGE > BPB >> BPA, demonstrating substantial differences in genotoxic effects among bisphenol analogs.

Risk Factor Calculation

The ecological risk of bisphenol analogues (BPA, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE) was further investigated based on the calculated RQ values. The RQ values for Bisphenols calculated as; 1,2 for BPA, 0,6 for BPB, 1,2 for BADGE and 0,4 for BFDGE. Results of the RQs of all tested compounds for both embryo and sperm toxicity were at BPA and BADGE have high risk (RQ >1), BPB and BFDGE moderately toxic for sea urchins.

4. Discussion

This study represents the first investigation on toxicity of bisphenols analogues on sea urchin *A. lixula*. In our current study, the environmental concentrations of BPs (BPB, BPA, BADGE and BFDGE) were tested. The present study provides an evaluation of the toxic, cytotoxic, genotoxic, and developmental effects of BPA and its analogs BPB, BADGE and BFDGE in

Arbacia lixula, using sperm, embryo, and larval endpoints. By assessing development of embryo, fertilization success, mitotic activity, cell cycle distribution, chromosomal damage and offspring quality, this study offers a comprehensive insight into the differential biological impacts of BPA substitutes compared to BPA itself.

Fertilization success showed that a highly sensitive endpoint, particularly for BPA exposure. The sharp, concentration-dependent decline in fertilized egg percentages following BPA treatment indicates a strong spermyotoxic effect. Similar inhibitory effects of BPA on fertilization have been reported in sea urchins and other marine invertebrates, supporting the notion that BPA can directly disrupt early reproductive events at environmentally relevant concentrations (Arslan & Parlak 2008). In contrast, BPB induced only moderate reductions, while BADGE and BFDGE exerted minor effects on fertilization, suggesting compound-specific interactions with sperm physiology. Embryonic mitotic activity (%MPE) was significantly reduced by all tested bisphenol compounds, clearly demonstrating their cytotoxic potential. This reduction was accompanied by a concomitant increase in the proportion of embryos arrested in interphase (%IE), indicating that bisphenol exposure interferes with normal cell cycle progression. The parallel decrease in mitosis and accumulation of cells in interphase strongly suggests the activation of cell cycle checkpoints, in response to cellular stress or DNA damage. Alterations in the metaphase/anaphase (M/A) ratio further supported the presence of mitotic disturbances. The pronounced increase in M/A ratio observed particularly for BPB and BADGE points to a metaphase arrest, potentially associated with spindle assembly checkpoint activation or microtubule dysfunction. Such mitotic alterations are consistent with previous studies reporting bisphenol-induced disruption of microtubule dynamics and chromosomal segregation. Genotoxicity, assessed as the percentage of embryos exhibiting mitotic bridges [$\%E(+mb) \geq 1$], revealed clear dose-dependent responses for all bisphenol compounds, with BADGE and BFDGE showing the highest genotoxic potency. The strong linear dose-response relationship observed for BADGE highlights its marked ability to induce chromosomal damage even at low concentrations. BPB also elicited substantial genotoxic effects, whereas BPA induced only limited damage, becoming evident at the highest concentration tested. BPA and BPB exerted the strongest embryotoxic effects, resulting in severe malformations or developmental arrest at low concentrations. BADGE showed moderate toxicity, while BFDGE was consistently the least disruptive compound, although high concentrations still led to a significant decline in normal larval development. These findings highlight that different bisphenol analogs affect distinct stages of development with varying intensity: BPA impaired fertilization and larval development, while BADGE and BFDGE exerted stronger effects at the cellular and genotoxic levels.

From an environmental perspective, the observed effects at low $\mu\text{g/L}$ concentrations raise serious concerns regarding the ecological safety of bisphenol analogs in marine environments. BPA and its substitutes are frequently detected in coastal waters, sediments, and biota, particularly in areas impacted by industrial discharge and urban runoff. The present results challenge the assumption that BPA analogs represent safer alternatives, especially BPB and BADGE exhibited equal or greater cytotoxic and genotoxic effects than BPA. Given the ecological importance of early life stages for population recruitment, disruptions in fertilization, cell division and larval development may have long-term consequences for marine invertebrate populations. The sensitivity of *A. lixula* embryos highlights their suitability as sentinel organisms for monitoring emerging contaminants and supports the inclusion of bisphenol analogs in regulatory risk assessment frameworks. As reported by Czarny-Krzywińska et al., (2023) the environmental concentrations of BPA and analogs have been detected in surface water samples at 1-68.900 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in wastewater at 0.44-16.600 μg . Considering the

environmental levels specified and the LOEC, NOEC, and EC50 (values we have presented, it has been demonstrated that the environmental concentrations of BPA and its analogues (BPB, BADGE and BFDGE) pose an ecological risk. To derive the water quality criteria of BPs, it is essential to obtain necessary aquatic toxicity data, especially chronic toxicity data pertaining to growth and development. For this reason, the tested concentrations in this study (0,1 -2 µg/L) were chosen considering their environmental availability. Results of toxicity test shown in Table II. According to the criteria from “the globally harmonized system of classification and labeling of chemicals (GHS)” (GHS 2019), chemicals with EC_{50} (or LC_{50}) < 1 mg/L were considered as Warning-class I. Therefore, BPs (BPA, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE) were considered a class I toxic substance for *A. lixula*.

Czarny et al. (2021) studied the toxic effect of BPB on two cyanobacteria, and found that the EC_{50} were 36.5–40.3 mg/L. Apparently, the *P. lividus* were more sensitive to BPB than cyanobacteria. This finding was compared the result reported by Chen et al. who found that the EC_{50} value of BPB to *D. magna* was 5.50 mg/L (Chen et al. 2002) showed that sea urchin larvae more sensitive than *D. magna*. Unfortunately, to our knowledge, there are no other studies on the acute toxicity of BPB to sea urchins. The above-mentioned studies indicate that BPA analogs might be more toxic than BPA to aquatic organisms.

Çakal Arslan (2025) were performed toxicity tests with BPA, BPS, BPF, BPAF and BPB on the embryos of commercial bivalves (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) and the toxicity of, the most important industrial chemicals synthesized for different applications instead of BPA, were measured in terms of embryogenesis success and median effective concentration (EC50). The EC50 values were calculated as: 0.476 mg-BPA/L, 0.558 µg-BPS/L, 0.410 µg-BPF/L, 0.509 µg-BPAF/L and 0.419 µg-BPB/L.

Limited information is available regarding the occurrence, distribution, and fate of BADGE and BFDGE in the environment (Inoue et al., 2001). BADGE and BFDGE were found in [river water](#) from China, at concentrations of 0.35 and 0.14 µg/L (Jiao et al., 2012). Two studies conducted in Spain found BADGE and BFDGE in the influent of wastewater treatment plants at concentrations ranging from 0.32 to 50 µg/L, (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2007).

Previously, the effects of BPA on echinoderms reported by Kunsman et al., (2025). Kunsman et al. (2025) investigated the toxic effects of BPA (1 µg/L, 10 µg/L, 100 µg/L and 1000 µg/L) on *Lytechinus variegatus* and *Arbacia punctulata*. The researchers also stated that the EC 50 values were above 1000 µg/L for *A. punctulata* and 260 µg/L for *L. variegatus*. The embryotoxicity results we have conducted are consistent with the researchers' data, but according to the BPA EC 50 value we calculated as 0,196 (sperm)-0,869 (embryo) µg-BPA/L for *P. lividus*. The fact that the concentrations evaluated in our study (Czarny-Krzyżmińska et al., 2023) are at environmental levels stated in the literature makes our study important. According to previous and current literature, BPA EC50 values in sea urchin embryos range from 1.56 µg/L in *Echinometra lucunter* (da Silva et al. 2019) to 1210 µg/L in *Arbacia lixula* (Tato et al., 2018). When these results are compared with the available data, comparable results were found, but *P. lividus* was shown to be more sensitive than other species (0,869 µg/L) .

The study by Wang et al. (2024) study, the acute toxicity of BPB was investigated using three aquatic organisms, *Tetrademus obliquus*, *Daphnia magna* and *Danio rerio*. Researcher reported that *Daphnia magna* was the most sensitive organism with a EC50 of 3.93 mg/L and BPB restricted the body length of parent *Daphnia magna* and reduced the total number of broods and neonates for 21 days chronic toxicity. Results by Wang et al. (2024) indicated that

The NOEC of BPB to *Daphnia magna* was 0.01 mg/L. Furthermore, the ecological risk of BPB was reported a moderate risk at. This study, when compared with the results of our biotests conducted with *P. lividus*, reveals the following: considering the EC50 value (0.311 µg/L) and the NOEC value (0.002 µg/L) of BPB for embryos, *P. lividus* embryos are more sensitive than *D. magna*. Furthermore, a comparison of the calculated RQ values indicates that environmental BPB concentrations pose a high, rather than moderate, risk.

As shown from the toxicity result in Table II. Study was comparable to the result reported by Chen et al. who found that the 48 h EC50 value of BPB to *D. magna* was 5.50 mg/L (Chen et al. 2022). For *D. rerio*, the 96 h LC50 value was 4.13 mg/L. In the study by Benas & Çakal Arslan (2024), three analogues BPB, BADGE and BFDGE were evaluated to investigate their ecotoxicological effects on the marine phytoplankton species *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*. *P. tricorutum* was exposed to different concentrations of BPB, BADGE and BFDGE analogues and the IC50/EC50 values of three BPA analogues were reported as: 3.91 mg-BPA/L, 7.83 mg-BPB/L, 5.69 mg-BFDGE/L, 11.71 mg-BADGE/L. The results revealed that BPB, BFDGE and BADGE showed lower toxicity to *P. tricorutum* compared to BPA algal growth inhibition (3.91 mg-BPA/L). Unfortunately, to our knowledge, there are no other studies on the acute, chronic and cytotoxic/genotoxicity of BPB, BADGE and BFDGE to sea urchin *P. lividus*. Our research has demonstrated that BPA, as well as BPB, BADGE and BFDGE, cause embryotoxicity, spermyotoxicity, and genotoxicity in *P. lividus*. However, embryological analysis revealed that BPB is significantly more harmful than BPA and others. The data obtained indicate that *A. lixula* is more sensitive than other species. Considering the similarities in early development between sea urchin species and humans, we believe this warrants further investigation.

5. Conclusions

In our study, we found that there is insufficient data regarding the possible toxic effects of BPA analogs on sea urchin embryos. Consequently, the toxic effects and ecological risks of bisphenol analogs on the sea urchin species *Arbacia lixula*, which holds significant importance in aquatic ecosystems, have been determined. Based on the calculated Risk Quotient (RQ) values, bisphenol compounds all pose a high ecological risk to *Arbacia lixula*. These findings highlight the pressing environmental hazard posed by bisphenols, even those considered as safer alternatives to BPA. The study underscores the significant reproductive risks posed by bisphenols in marine environments, particularly concerning their effects on fertilization and larval development in sea urchins. This suggests that even if fertilization occurs, the resultant embryos may be compromised, leading to high rates of deformities and mortality that can threaten population sustainability. The differential toxicity rankings for embryos and sperm indicate that while BPA, BPB, BADGE and BFDGE are particularly harmful to embryonic development, BPB poses a greater risk to sperm integrity. The significant reductions in normal pluteus development and the high mortality rates at elevated concentrations underscore the urgent need for monitoring and regulating bisphenol levels in marine environments to protect aquatic life and maintain ecological balance.

6. Author Contributions

Authors contributed equally to this work. Conducting bioassays, microscopic observations, interpreting data and authoring the article.

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Ethical approval

"This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors."

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